

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2023.6
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7924812
 UDC: 331.1
 JEL: E24, J24, J28

THE INFLUENCE OF WORK SPIRIT AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON EMPLOYEE WORK PRODUCTIVITY WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS INTERVENING VARIABLES IN DPRD SECRETARIAT LABUHANBATU DISTRICT

ВПЛИВ ТРУДОВОГО НАСТРОЮ ТА ТРУДОВОЇ ДИСЦИПЛІНИ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ІЗ ЗАДОВОЛЕНІСТЮ РОБОТОЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНИМИ ЗМІННИМИ В СЕКРЕТАРІАТІ DPRD ОКРУГ ЛАБУХАНБАТУ

Salman Faris

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-9679-1729

Bayu Utomo

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-9840-5844

Syaifuddin

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-6977-5256

Alex Tribuana Sutanto

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
 ORCID: 0000-0002-9490-7150

Received 02.02.2023

Salman Faris, Bayu Utomo, Syaifuddin, Alex Tribuana Sutanto. Вплив трудового настрою та трудової дисципліни на продуктивність праці працівників із задоволеністю роботою як проміжними змінними в Секретаріаті DPRD округ Лабуханбату. Оглядова стаття.

Дослідження має на меті визначити, чи впливають робочий ентузіазм і трудова дисципліна на продуктивність праці співробітників через задоволеність роботою як проміжну змінну в Секретаріаті DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency. Дослідження проводилося на 53 співробітниках за методикою насиченої вибірки. Використана техніка збору даних: первинні дані у формі анкет та вторинні дані, отримані шляхом вивчення документації. Техніка аналізу даних використовувала кількісні дані, які були оброблені за допомогою програми SPSS версії 25, а саме t-тест, тест Собея та аналіз шляхів. Для майбутніх дослідників це дослідження слід розвивати ширше, щоб отримати сильніші емпіричні результати шляхом додавання інших змінних, які впливають на продуктивність праці співробітників.

Ключові слова: моральний дух, трудова дисципліна, задоволеність роботою, продуктивність праці

Salman Faris, Bayu Utomo, Syaifuddin, Alex Tribuana Sutanto. The Influence of Work Spirit and Work Discipline on Employee Work Productivity With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables in DPRD Secretariat Labuhanbatu District. Review article.

Study aims to determine whether work enthusiasm and work discipline affect employee work productivity through job satisfaction as an intervening variable at the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. For future researchers, this research should be developed more broadly to obtain stronger empirical results by adding other variables that affect employee work productivity.

Keywords: morale, work discipline, job satisfaction, work productivity

Human resource management (HRM) is a field of management that specifically studies human relationships and roles in organizations. This is because human resource management regulates the workforce in the organization, so that organizational goals and employee job satisfaction are realized. Every company always tries so that employees can excel in the form of providing maximum work productivity. Work productivity indicates that the individual is a comparison of output effectiveness (maximum performance achievement) with the efficiency of one input (labor) of work which includes quality, quantity in a certain time. Based on the results of preliminary research at the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat, it was found that employee productivity tended to decrease, not in line with the increase in the number of employees. Of course this is a serious concern for agencies in terms of employee productivity. The decline in employee work productivity is due to employees who are not optimal at work, one of which is not creating employee job satisfaction so that employee morale and discipline decrease. This can be seen from the work done is not scheduled by the employee, resulting in a buildup of work, which makes employees confused about which work should take precedence, while the work must be completed as soon as possible.

In order to increase the productivity of the employees of the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat, the organization must align organizational goals with the personal goals of each employee. Robbins (2013) states that employees with a high level of job satisfaction have a positive attitude towards their work, whereas someone with a low level of job satisfaction tends to have a negative attitude towards their work. Job satisfaction is the level of individual satisfaction that they get rewarded fairly from various aspects of the work situation of the organization where they work. Organizations that are strengthened by employee morale will be directly proportional to the productivity and work performance of these employees which will ultimately lead to organizational growth. Therefore the organization needs to maintain employee morale to remain stable, if employees have good morale then the work of the employees they carry out will be completed quickly and do the work more actively and optimally.

Besides that, to maximize employee work productivity supported by work discipline, employee work discipline is very important. , individuals are able to behave by choosing actions that are determined or appropriate. For this reason, efforts are needed to raise work discipline and awareness of employee work discipline, especially increasing self-discipline, because the best discipline is self-discipline.

The main part

Based on the phenomena that occur in the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency, the purpose of this research is as follows:

- To find out and analyze the influence of work enthusiasm on To find out and analyze the effect of work discipline on job satisfaction.

- To know and analyze the effect of morale on work productivity.
- To know and analyze work discipline on work productivity.
- To know and analyze the effect of job satisfaction on work productivity.
- To find out and analyze the effect of morale on work productivity through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
- To know and analyze the effect of work discipline on work productivity through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
- To find out and analyze the effect of work discipline on work productivity through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

The results obtained from this research are expected to broaden the reader's knowledge about how to overcome problems related to work productivity, can be input to agencies to increase work productivity, improve management so that they can maximize work so that work productivity can be increased.

METHOD. This research is included in associative research with a quantitative approach. This study examines the relationship between the variables Morale (X1) and Work Discipline (X2) to the variable Work Productivity (Y) and job satisfaction (Z) as the intervening variable. In this study the approach used is a quantitative approach because the data used to analyze the influence between variables is expressed in numbers or on a numerical scale (Kuncoro, 2011, in Wulandari, 2015). In contrast, the data source used is primary data and secondary data. The population in this study was all permanent employees (PNS) at the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat, which were recorded in December 2022 totaling 53 people.

Table 1. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	34.394	7.098		4.846	0.000
	Morale	0.390	0.094	0.425	4.147	0.000
	Work discipline	0.182	0.085	0.097	4.961	0.040
	Work satisfaction	0.122	0.152	0.152	4.494	0.039

a. Dependent Variable: Work productivity
 Source: authors' own elaboration

RESULT. SUB MODEL T TEST RESULTS.

In the table, the t statistical test is obtained, as follows:

- 1) Variable job satisfaction (Z), with a probability level of 0.039. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.039 < \alpha = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis that the Job Satisfaction variable has a significant effect on Work Productivity.
- 2) Morale variable (X1), with a probability level of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.000 > \alpha = 0.05$, so reject the hypothesis that the variable morale has a significant effect on work productivity.

- 3) Work discipline variable (X2), with a probability level of 0.040. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.040 > \alpha = 0.05$, so reject the hypothesis which states that work discipline variables have a significant effect on work productivity.

1.1.1. Sobel Test.

Testing the mediation hypothesis can also be carried out with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the Sobel test (Sobel test). The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{b^2SE_a^2 + a^2SE_b^2}} \tag{1}$$

where a – regression coefficient of the independent variable on the mediating variable;

b – regression coefficient of the mediating variable on the dependent variable;

SE_a – standard error of estimation from the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable;

SE_b – standard error of estimation of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable.

The following are the results of the Sobel test with the variable morale on work productivity through job satisfaction.

$$t = \frac{0.188 \times 0.152}{\sqrt{(0.152^2 \times 0.129^2) + (0.188^2 \times 0.081^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.188 \times 0.152}{\sqrt{0.0003844737 + 0.000231892}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.028576}{0.0006163657}$$

$$t = 4.636.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, the t value of 4.636 is obtained, so that the t value is 4.636 > t table 4.447. It can be concluded that

the variable job satisfaction is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of morale on work productivity.

The following are the results of the Sobel test with work discipline variables on work productivity through job satisfaction.

$$t = \frac{0.179 \times 0.152}{\sqrt{(0.152^2 \times 0.118^2) + (0.179^2 \times 0.081^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.179 \times 0.152}{\sqrt{0.0003217001 + 0.000210221}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.027208}{0.0005319211}$$

$$t = 5.115.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, a t value of 5.115 is obtained, so that a t value of 5.115 > t table is 4.447, it can be concluded that the variable job satisfaction is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of work discipline on work productivity.

3.1. Path Analysis.

The path diagram of the structure model II is obtained as follows:

Figure 1. Path Analysis
Source: authors' own elaboration

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence of Work Morale (X1) on Work Productivity (Y) is 0.425. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of morale (X1) on work productivity (Y) through job satisfaction (Z), is 0.188 x 0.152 = 0.028. Then the total effect given by the Work Morale (X1) variable on Work Productivity (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely 0.425 + 0.028 = 0.45. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.425 and the indirect effect is 0.028, which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the variable Morale (X1) through job satisfaction (Z) has no significant effect on work productivity (Y).

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence of Work Discipline (X2) on Work Productivity (Y) is 0.097. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of work discipline (X2) on work productivity

(Y) through job satisfaction (Z), is 0.179 x 0.097 = 0.017. Then the total effect given by the Work Discipline variable (X2) on Work Productivity (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely 0.097 + 0.017 = 0.114. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.097 and the indirect effect is 0.017, which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the variable Work Discipline (X2) through job satisfaction (Z) has no significant effect on Work Productivity (Y).

Conclusions

From this study it can be concluded as follows:

a. Morale has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Secretariat of the DPRD Kab. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that giving morale can increase employee job satisfaction.

b. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the better the work discipline of employees can lead to job satisfaction.

c. Morale has a positive and significant effect on work productivity at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that giving morale to employees can increase work productivity.

d. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on work productivity at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the better work discipline can increase employee work productivity.

e. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work productivity at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the higher job satisfaction can increase work productivity.

f. The effect of morale on work productivity of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab.

Labuhanbatu will be smaller if done through job satisfaction. The direct effect of morale on employee work productivity is greater than the indirect effect of morale on work productivity. It can be concluded that job satisfaction is not able to mediate the effect of morale on work productivity.

g. The effect of work discipline on the work productivity of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu will be smaller if done through job satisfaction. The direct effect of work discipline on work productivity is greater than the indirect effect of work discipline on work productivity. It can be concluded that job satisfaction is not able to mediate the effect of work discipline on work productivity.

Based on the discussion on this study, it can be concluded that providing good morale accompanied by work discipline can increase employee job satisfaction and also work productivity. Furthermore, for future researchers, this research should be developed more broadly to obtain stronger empirical results by adding other variables that affect employee work productivity.

Abstract

This study aims to determine whether work enthusiasm and work discipline affect employee work productivity through job satisfaction as an intervening variable at the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant influence between work enthusiasm and job satisfaction, 2) there is a significant effect between work discipline variables on job satisfaction, 3) there is a significant effect between work enthusiasm and work productivity, 4) there is a significant effect between work discipline variables on work productivity, 5) there is a significant influence between job satisfaction variables on work productivity, 6) job satisfaction variables cannot influence work spirit variables on work productivity, 7) job satisfaction variables cannot influence work discipline variables on work productivity.

Список літератури:

1. Agustini, Fauzia. (2011). *Advanced human resource management (First Edition)*. Medan: Madenatera Publisher.
2. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu. (2009). *Organization and basic motivation to increase productivity*. 7th Printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
3. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2013). *Company human resource management (12th Printing)*. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
4. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2012). *Company human resource management*. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
5. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2017). *Company human resource management*. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
6. Sugiyono. (2012). *Business research methods*. London: Alphabet.
7. Sutrisno, Eddie. (2011). *Organizational Culture (1st Edition)*. Jakarta: Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group).
8. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2011). *Research methods for business & economy*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
9. Sugiyono. (2018). *Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alphabet.
10. Ghozali, Imam. (2018). *Application of multi variate analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Jakarta: Diponegoro University Publisher.
11. Anwar, Sanusi. (2011). *Business Research Methodology*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat. Argentina. Analysis of the Influence of Job Satisfaction and Motivation on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable in the Customs and Excise Service Office of Customs and Excise Type Middle Customs B Medan. *Economist Journal*, 17(2).
12. Ghozali, Imam. (2016). *Multivariate Analysis Application With IBM SPSS 23 Program (Edition 8)*. VIII print. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.

13. Hasibuan, Malayu S. (2008). Organization and Motivation: Basics of Increasing Productivity. Earth Script: Jakarta.
14. Husein Umar. (2013). Research methods for Thesis and Thesis. Rajawali, Jakarta.
15. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2013). Research methods for Business and Economics. Edition 3. Jakarta: Erlangga.
16. Newstrom, John W. & Keith Davis. (2004). Organizational Behavior 7th Edition. Jakarta: Erlangga.
17. Yukl, Gary. (2009). Leadership in Organizations. Translated by: Budi Supriyanto. Jakarta: Index.
18. Muhammad Isa, Adek Irawan. (2019). The Effect of Development on Employee Performance at the Mandailing Natal District Inspectorate Office. Journal of Economics & Sharia Economics, 2.

References:

1. Agustini, Fauzia. (2011). Advanced human resource management (First Edition). Medan: Madenatera Publisher [in English].
2. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu. (2009). Organization and basic motivation to increase productivity. 7th Printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara [in English].
3. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2013). Company human resource management (12th Printing). Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
4. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2012). Company human resource management. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
5. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2017). Company human resource management. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
6. Sugiyono. (2012). Business research methods. London: Alphabet [in English].
7. Sutrisno, Eddie. (2011). Organizational Culture (1st Edition). Jakarta: Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group) [in English].
8. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2011). Research methods for business & economy. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
9. Sugiyono. (2018). Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods. Bandung: Alphabet [in English].
10. Ghozali, Imam. (2018). Application of multi variate analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 Program. Jakarta: Diponegoro University Publisher [in English].
11. Anwar, Sanusi. (2011). Business Research Methodology. Jakarta: Salemba Empat. Argentina. Analysis of the Influence of Job Satisfaction and Motivation on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable in the Customs and Excise Service Office of Customs and Excise Type Middle Customs B Medan. Economist Journal, 17(2) [in English].
12. Ghazali, Imam. (2016). Multivariate Analysis Application With IBM SPSS 23 Program (Edition 8). VIII print. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency [in English].
13. Hasibuan, Malayu S. (2008). Organization and Motivation: Basics of Increasing Productivity. Earth Script: Jakarta [in English].
14. Husein Umar. (2013). Research methods for Thesis and Thesis. Rajawali, Jakarta [in English].
15. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2013). Research methods for Business and Economics. Edition 3. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
16. Newstrom, John W., & Keith Davis. (2004). Organizational Behavior 7th Edition. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
17. Yukl, Gary. (2009). Leadership in Organizations. Translated by: Budi Supriyanto. Jakarta: Index [in English].
18. Muhammad Isa, Adek Irawan. (2019). The Effect of Development on Employee Performance at the Mandailing Natal District Inspectorate Office. Journal of Economics & Sharia Economics, 2 [in English].

Посилання на статтю:

Salman Faris. *The Influence of Work Spirit and Work Discipline on Employee Work Productivity With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables in DPRD Secretariat Labuhanbatu District* / Salman Faris, Bayu Utomo, Syaifuddin, Alex Tribuana Sutanto // *Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал.* – 2023. – № 1 (65). – С. 49-53. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No1/49.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2023.6. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7924812.

Reference a Journal Article:

Salman Faris. *The Influence of Work Spirit and Work Discipline on Employee Work Productivity With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables in DPRD Secretariat Labuhanbatu District* / Salman Faris, Bayu Utomo, Syaifuddin, Alex Tribuana Sutanto // *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal.* – 2023. – № 1 (65). – P. 49-53. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No1/49.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2023.6. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7924812.

